

geocoder: an R package to store and access geographic data in MongoDB

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Introduction

Geocodes (Goldberg, Wilson, and Knoblock 2007) are spatial references which are used to identify points or boundaries in a geographic coordinate system. Finding geocodes is a cumbersome and repeated task for data scientists. In the case of the United Kingdom, despite the availability of “open geography portal” (National Statistics 2016), data scientists need to locate the relevant source, which could be typically an ESRI shape or sometimes a comma separated values (CSV) file. In the case of those who use R as a data science tool, this also means processing these files repeatedly. Having these geocodes handy which can be easily accessed is what geospatial database management systems (DBMS) such as PostGIS and MongoDB should be doing. The idea of having an R package that can facilitate this is the reason for a missing R package called `geocoder`. In the age of availability of wide range of SQL/NoSQL and other big data oriented DBMS'es, finding geocodes should be easier.

Motivation

The Turing Institute's eAtlas project (“Turing Geovisualization Engine” 2019) is focused on visualizing spatially referenced datasets. It would be much easier to get the geographic data from datasets using databases rather than data science workflows in R/Python. Whilst developing a web based geovisualization eAtlas and allowing users to “load” their datasets in different formats, it would be great to detect geocodes and find coordinate data (such as longitude and latitudes) “automatically”. As it stands, there is no such open API (Application Programming Interface) to query for such geographic data and availability of such data locally (to the application) is becoming a need.

Relevant technology

The standardisation of storage and access model of two-dimensional geographic references by both Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) and International Organization for Standardisation (ISO) means programmers can define objects which represent these standards. This standard is known as Simple Features. In the case of R, the well known package called `sf` (Pebesma 2018) defines the standard and provides tools to manage geographic data in R. MongoDB is one of the DBMS'es which also support this standard.

MongoDB comes with built-in geospatial indexing and querying (Ameri et al. 2014) around GeoJSON (Butler et al. 2016), which is another standard built on top of Simple Features. MongoDB accepts GeoJSON formatted coordinates, and database indices can be created which facilitate fast spatial queries. As a data interchange format, GeoJSON is also widely supported by mapping libraries (Page 2015). GeoJSON is JSON which is natively supported (read) by JavaScript and might be the reason for its wider popularity.

UK geocodes case

UK Office of National Statistics Open Geography Portal contains various files which are used by data scientists to plot data on maps. Details of different layers etc.

Round trip through MongoDB

To showcase the capabilities of `geocoder` package, we can do a round trip data processing from a pseudo-standard R spatial `sf` class back to itself through MongoDB's geospatial querying. That is:

- take a shapefile from UK's Open Geography Portal and write it into a MongoDB collection and create a spatial index on it using an `sf` object.
- reassemble the data from MongoDB queries back to an `sf` object.

One of the UK census boundaries is called Middle Superr Output Area (MSOA), which can be found here.

```
msoa.folder = file.path(tempdir(), "msoa_folder")
msoa.zip = file.path(tempdir(), "msoa.zip")
if(!exists(msoa.file)) {
  download.file(
    paste0("https://opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/",
          "f341dcfd94284d58aba0a84daf2199e9_0.zip"),
    msoa.zip)
  unzip(msoa.zip, exdir = msoa.folder)
}
# read the shape file using `sf`
msoa.sf = sf::read_sf(
  list.files(msoa.folder, pattern = "England_and_Wales.shp"))
class(msoa.sf)
# substring(geojsonsf::sf_geojson(msoa.sf[1,]), 1, 350)
```

The data is ready in a clean `sf` object and we can use `geocoder::gc_import_sf` to import into MongoDB:

```
geocoder::gc_import_sf(msoa.sf, collection = "msoa")
```

We can now query the database with lists of MSOA codes and easily return GeoJSON formatted “features” ready to be reassembled into `sf`.

```
r = gc_find(data.frame(properties.msoa01cd="E02000998"), collection = "msoa")
class(r)
# [1] "data.frame"
substr(r, 1, 200)
# [1] "Feature"
# [2] "list(objectid = 998, msoa01cd = \"E02000998\", ..."
```

Find geocodes with spatial reference

```
# head(st_coordinates(st_geometry(msoa.sf[1,])))
# code for point -0.09640594 51.52283
qry <- '[
  {
    "$geoNear" : {
      "near" : { "type" : "Point", "coordinates" : [ -0.09640594, 51.52283 ] },
      "distanceField" : "dist.calculated",
      "maxDistance" : 1,
      "spherical" : true
    }
  }
]'
```

```
r = msoa.collection$aggregate(pipeline = qry)
```


Figure 1: A sample from dataset plotted from MongoDB (left) and memory (right)

```
r$properties$msoa01cd
# "E02000001" "E02000576"
```

The returned values are two different geometries which both correctly include the point in the query.

Reproducible example

A reproducible (as the UK msoa example is too large) for this manuscript would be a slice of Uber's Vancouver land area price.

```
# geojson file from Uber
library(sf)
v.path = file.path(tempdir(), "vancouver.json")
if(!exists(v.path)) {
  v.url = paste0("https://github.com/layik/geocoder/releases/",
                "download/data/v10.geojson")
  download.file(v.url, v.path)
}

v = geojsonsf::geojson_sf(v.path)
vancouver = mongolite::mongo("vancouver")
# plot(v[8, ], axes = TRUE)
```

Let us retrieve the data and plot the land:

```
vancouver$drop() # if exists
geocoder::gc_import_sf(v, collection = "vancouver")
#> Writing '10' documents...
#> There are '10' documents in collection: vancouver
#> [1] 10
r = vancouver$iterate(query = '{"properties.growth":0.2781}')
r.sf = geojsonsf::geojson_sf(r$json())
```

Visual check that both entries are the same:

Figure 2: Vancouver real estate dataset and sample area.

R vs MongoDB

We can look at a use-case where instead of searching through geocodes in memory we query a local database. For example, instead of loading one or more files and converting them into `sf` or similar like objects in R, we search an spatial index in a MongoDB instance. Lets assume you have loaded the Vancouver real estate dataset into R and the same dataset has been imported using into MongoDB using `geocoder::gc_import_sf()` function.

First we can make sure that a simple query returns the same number of rows:

```
v$count('{"properties.growth": 0.2724}') ==  
  length(which(sf$growth == 0.2724))  
# [1] TRUE
```

It is also fair to assume that for a data scientist to make a spatial query, we have to load the dataset into memory first. We know that in-memory databases are built to manage in-memory access to data, but that is not the focus at the moment.

```
url = paste0("https://github.com/uber-common/deck.gl-data/",  
            "blob/master/examples/geojson/vancouver-blocks.json?raw=true")  
v.path = file.path(tempdir(), "v.geojson")  
if(!file.exists(v.path)) {  
  download.file(url, destfile = v.path)  
}  
# sampling the data  
sf = st_read(v.path)  
cent = st_centroid(st_as_sfc(st_bbox(sf)))  
cent = st_transform(cent, 3488)  
circle = st_buffer(cent, dist = 3000)  
circle = st_transform(circle, 4326)
```

The dataset is land boundaries in Vancouver with two variables: value per square meter and growth rate. We will use a sample of it by drawing a circle in the center of the boundary box of the whole dataset:

```
plot(st_geometry(sf))  
plot(circle, col = "red", add = T)
```

Let us now load the dataset into MongoDB and demonstrate a basic experiment, more sophisticated and richer geospatial queries is not the focus of this document but rather to show the new R package `geocoder` functions:

```
v = mongolite::mongo(collection = "test_geocoder")
v$drop() # just in case
geocoder::gc_import_sf(sf, collection = "test_geocoder")
# scoping
sffind = NULL
vfind = NULL
# load and search
sf_search = function() {
  sf = st_read(v.path)
  # in memory search (R)
  sffind <- st_intersection(sf, st_as_sf(circle))
}
# Mongo search
mongo_search = function() {
  vfind <- v$iterate(paste0('{
    "geometry": {
      "$geoIntersects": {
        "$geometry": ',
        geojsonsf::sf_geojson(st_as_sf(circle), atomise = TRUE )
      },
    }
  }'))
}
mb = microbenchmark::microbenchmark(
  sf_search(),
  mongo_search(),
  times = 50
)
```

Conclusion

Looking at the results, which understandably varies considerably between the two methods because in the case of searching in memory, although it is faster, we need to load the whole data (1.5mb) into memory first. To paint the whole picture, under the same circumstances, even if the whole data is queried, searching through MongoDB would only be three times slower. Figure (3) assists in doing a visual check of the two methods.

```
#> Unit: microseconds
#>      expr      min      lq      mean      median      uq
#> sf_search() 291697.850 305944.38 319004.828 314953.106 327706.25
#> mongo_search()   870.567   981.51  1079.563  1026.937  1085.74
#>      max neval
#> 365695.229   50
#>  3515.473   50
```


Figure 3: Vancouver real estate dataset sample area from sf’s ‘intersection’ (left) and MongoDB ‘geoIntersects’ (right). The way the two functions work can clearly be seen but the number of polygons returned are equal.

References

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